

1 **Abrupt shoaling of the nutricline in response to massive**
2 **freshwater flooding at the onset of the last interglacial sapropel**
3 **event**

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21 **Abstract**

22 [1] A detailed assessment of the respective roles of production, export, and subsequent
23 preservation of organic carbon (C_{org}) in the eastern Mediterranean (EMED) sediments during
24 the formation of sapropels remains elusive. Here we present new micropaleontological results
25 for both surface samples taken at several locations in the EMED and last interglacial sapropel
26 S5 from core LC21 in the southeastern Aegean Sea. A strong exponential anticorrelation
27 between relative abundances of the lower photic zone coccolithophore *Florisphaera profunda*
28 in the surface sediments and modern concentrations of chlorophyll a (Chl-a) at the sea surface
29 suggests that *F. profunda* percentages can be used to track past productivity changes in the
30 EMED. Prior to S5 deposition, an abrupt and large increase of *F. profunda* percentages in
31 LC21 coincided (within the multi-decadal resolution of the records) with the marked
32 freshening of EMED surface waters. This suggests a strong coupling between freshwater-
33 bound surface to intermediate water (density) stratification and enhanced upward advection
34 of nutrients to the base of the photic zone, fuelling a productive deep chlorophyll maximum
35 (DCM) underneath a nutrient-starved surface layer. Our findings imply that (at least) at the
36 onset of sapropel formation physical and biogeochemical processes likely operated in
37 tandem, enabling high C_{org} accumulation at the seafloor.

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44 1. Introduction

45 [2] The Mediterranean Sea is a semi-enclosed marginal sea of the Atlantic Ocean with a
46 generally well-ventilated water column owing to multiple sites of intermediate to deep
47 convection and a vigorous basin-wide thermohaline circulation [Zavatarielli and Mellor,
48 1995; Pinardi and Masetti, 2000]. The latter is largely driven by excess evaporation and
49 related water mass transformation within the eastern Mediterranean (EMED) (i.e., east of the
50 Strait of Sicily) and is thus very sensitive to changes in the freshwater budget of that sector of
51 the basin [e.g., Rohling and Bryden, 1992]. EMED sapropels are organic-rich layers that
52 reflect curtailed bottom water ventilation [Rohling, 1994; Cramp and O'Sullivan, 1999; Negri
53 et al., 2009] during periods of orbital precession minima [Revel et al., 2010; Ziegler et al.,
54 2010], in response to enhanced monsoon-fuelled river discharge along the North African
55 margin [e.g., Rohling et al., 2002, 2004; Osborne et al., 2008]. The freshwater-bound
56 weakening of the EMED thermohaline circulation inhibited oxygen supply to the deep sea,
57 thereby promoting organic carbon (C_{org}) preservation at depth [e.g., Rossignol-Strick et al.,
58 1982; Rohling, 1994; De Lange et al., 2008]. Other studies suggest that enhanced primary
59 productivity in the upper water column during periods of sapropel deposition increased the
60 downward export of C_{org} , in turn, enabling deep-water anoxia [e.g., De Lange and ten Haven,
61 1983; Calvert et al., 1992].

62 [3] Although the debate is often presented in polarized terms of “anoxia” versus
63 “productivity”, the actual evidence instead alludes to a combination of these influences,
64 which can be viewed as components of a single underlying hydrographic response to
65 freshwater forcing [Rohling and Gieskes, 1989; Rohling, 1994]. For example, microfossil
66 assemblages [Rohling and Gieskes, 1989; Castradori, 1993; Kemp et al., 1999] and
67 geochemical data [Sachs and Repeta, 1999] in certain sapropels point to the occurrence of a
68 productive deep chlorophyll maximum (DCM) positioned underneath a nutrient-

69 impoverished mixed layer. The shoaling of the isopycnals in response to surface freshening
70 would then explain the upward advection of nutrients [Rohling and Gieskes, 1989] that were
71 either “concentrated” in the basin due to a sluggish thermohaline circulation [Sarmiento *et*
72 *al.*, 1988], accumulated over a considerable period of time prior to the deep-water ventilation
73 changes [Casford *et al.*, 2002], or “regenerated” under oxygen-depleted conditions [Slomp *et*
74 *al.*, 2002]. This picture is contrasted with the present-day strongly depleted EMED sediments
75 in C_{org} due to ultra-oligotrophic and phosphorus-starved surface waters [Krom *et al.*, 1991;
76 Turley *et al.*, 2000; D'Ortenzio and Ribera d'Alcalà, 2009], which is a reflection of a net
77 westward export of dissolved nutrients across the Strait of Sicily that is coupled with the
78 efficient anti-estuarine circulation (and vigorous deep ventilation) in the Mediterranean Sea
79 [Ignatiades *et al.*, 2009; Siokou-Frangou *et al.*, 2010].

80 [4] Clearly there is a tight interplay between physical and biogeochemical processes in
81 the EMED, suggesting that vertical fluxes and utilization of nutrients in the upper water
82 column may respond dramatically to perturbations of the basin's thermohaline circulation
83 (for example by freshwater forcing). Deciphering timing and magnitude of these responses is
84 critical for unraveling the mechanisms that control sapropel formation. Recent high-
85 resolution studies have detailed the picture of the physical processes associated with the
86 deposition of sapropels [Casford *et al.*, 2002, 2003; Rohling *et al.*, 2002, 2004, 2006; Marino
87 *et al.*, 2007, 2009], but there remains a need for similarly resolved reconstructions of the
88 contemporaneous productivity patterns.

89 [5] Here we focus on the last interglacial sapropel S5, a strongly developed anoxic event
90 in the EMED [Kemp *et al.*, 1999; Rohling *et al.*, 2002, 2004, 2006; Marino *et al.*, 2007;
91 Osborne *et al.*, 2008, 2010]. Sapropel S5, as opposed to the more recent S1 [Meroni *et al.*,
92 2001; Casford *et al.*, 2002, 2003], is intensively developed in terms of (i) freshwater forcing
93 [Rohling *et al.*, 2002], (ii) severity of the hydrographic responses throughout the basin

94 [Rohling *et al.*, 2006; Marino *et al.*, 2007] and (iii) accumulation of organic carbon (C_{org}) at
95 the seafloor [Kemp *et al.*, 1999; Struck *et al.*, 2001; Rohling *et al.*, 2006; Marino *et al.*, 2007].
96 The high signal to noise ratios in S5 make this anoxic event ideally suited for proxy-based
97 studies aimed at deciphering the causal mechanisms behind sapropel formation. Contrary to
98 the more extreme but less well-dated Pliocene sapropels [Passier *et al.*, 1999], records for S5
99 can be placed on an absolute timescale [Bar-Matthews *et al.*, 2000], allowing the duration of
100 processes to be more firmly assessed. Here we present new surface sediment coccolith results
101 along with downcore coccolith results through S5 from a high sedimentation rate site (LC21)
102 in the southeastern Aegean Sea. New and previously published data from LC21 [Marino *et*
103 *al.*, 2007] are used to investigate the response of EMED nutrient budget and primary
104 productivity in the upper water column to extensive freshwater-bound hydrographic changes.

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106 **2. Modern water mass and nutrient dynamics**

107 [6] The Atlantic surface waters that enter the Mediterranean Sea through the Strait of
108 Gibraltar subsequently flow into the EMED through the Strait of Sicily (Figure 1), and
109 progressively gain heat and salt along this path [Wüst, 1961; Malanotte-Rizzoli and Hecht,
110 1988]. During winter-spring, sustained heat loss in the Rhodes cyclonic gyre leads to the
111 formation of the Levantine Intermediate Water (LIW) [Hecht *et al.*, 1988; Theocharis *et al.*,
112 1999; Zervakis *et al.*, 2000; Hecht and Gertman, 2001]. LIW flows westward between 150
113 and 600 m water depth [Pinardi and Masetti, 2000] and pre-conditions deep water formation
114 in the northern sectors of the basin [Wu and Haines, 1996].

115 [7] The EMED features a permanent nutricline between the density surfaces of 29.00 –
116 29.05 and 29.15 isopycnals throughout the basin [Yilmaz and Tuğrul, 1998], that is a depth
117 ranging from 50 to 400 m in the southern Aegean Sea [Theocharis *et al.*, 1999]. Primary

118 productivity is fuelled by entrainment of nutrients from lower layers, especially by
119 wintertime vertical mixing [Krom *et al.*, 1992], and is higher in cyclonic regions such as, e.g.,
120 the Rhodes gyre, where doming of the isopycnals causes the nutricline to reach the base of
121 the photic zone. Situated between the cyclonic Rhodes gyre to the east and the cyclonic
122 Cretan gyre to the west (Figure 1), the site of core LC21 is characterized by a shallow
123 nutricline which almost crops out in winter [see, e.g., figure 8b in *Theocharis et al.*, 1999].

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125 **3. Material and methods**

126 [8] Sediment core LC21 (35°40'N, 26°35'E; 1522 m water depth, Figure 1) was
127 recovered in 1995 by R/V *Marion Dufresne* [Rothwell, 1995]. The chronology used here for
128 core LC21 through sapropel S5 follows *Marino et al.* [2007] and yields a temporal resolution
129 of $\sim 40 \pm 20$ yr cm^{-1} within S5.

130 [9] We analyzed S5, in core sections 5 and 6, at 2 cm spacing (102 samples) for the
131 relative abundances of the coccolith species *Florisphaera profunda* and *Helicosphaera*
132 *carteri*, and at coarser resolution (2 to 40 cm spacing) for absolute coccolith abundances. We
133 also assessed the modern distribution of *F. profunda* in EMED surface sediments based on
134 analyses of this taxon's relative abundances in 43 surface sediment samples retrieved during
135 R/V *Meteor* cruises M40 leg 4 (1998), M50 leg 3 (2001) and M52 leg 2 (2002); and during
136 the Biodeep01 and Biodeep02 cruises (1997) (Figure 2A). These new data supplement
137 previously published data (124 samples in total, Table S1 in the auxiliary material).

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139 **3.1. Calcareous nannofossil analyses**

140 [10] Quantitative analyses of calcareous nannofossil abundances were performed with a
141 polarized light microscope with $\times 1000$ magnification. The smear slides were prepared

142 following standard procedures on the <63 μ m sediment fraction for both core LC21 and
143 surface sediment samples. An average of ~680 (surface sediments) and ~350 (LC21
144 downcore record) coccolith specimen were counted for each sample.

145 [11] Absolute coccolith abundances were estimated for 10 samples of LC21 quantifying
146 the number of coccoliths in a portion of the filtered sediment samples [*Lototskaya et al.*,
147 1998]. Samples were prepared as follows: about 0.01 g of sediment was diluted in 100 ml of
148 tap-water and placed in an ultrasonic bath few seconds in order to disaggregate it. The
149 samples were then filtered through a Milipore membrane (47 mm diameter, 0.45 μ m pore
150 size) using a low pressure vacuum pump to obtain even distribution of the particles on the
151 filter. The filter was oven dried at 40°C for 1 h. Finally, a quarter of the filter was mounted
152 with Canadian balsam to make a permanent slide.

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154 **3.2. Chlorophyll a (Chl-a) concentrations**

155 [12] The annual composite data of chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) concentration used to calibrate
156 our coccolith-based proxies (Figure 2B), were extracted from the NASA Ocean Color and
157 Temperature Scanner (OCTS), the Coastal Zone Color Scanner (CZCS) experiment and the
158 Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor (SeaWiFS) project, in order to cover the period from
159 1986 to 2002 that corresponds to the different oceanographic cruises considered here (Table
160 S1 in the auxiliary material). The Chl-a data are distributed as a Level-3 Binned file product
161 (BIN), reprocessing No. 5, October 2011 [*Feldman and McClain*, 2011]. The annual
162 composites were downloaded from the <http://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/> website in
163 Hierarchical Data Format (HDF). The images have a resolution of 9 km² (4320×2160 pixels)
164 and were analyzed using SeaDAS [*Baith et al.*, 2001]. Information was extracted from the

165 pixels closest to the location of the surface sediment sample sites, and for each sample we
166 averaged the data of the year of the cruise and the year just before.

167

168 **4. Ecology of the selected coccolithophore species in the Mediterranean Sea**

169 [13] *Florisphaera profunda* inhabits the lower photic zone [Okada and Honjo, 1973;
170 Honjo and Okada, 1974; Okada and McIntyre, 1977; Matsuoka and Okada, 1989; Molfino
171 and McIntyre, 1990; Ujiie et al., 1991]. High relative abundances of this taxon are diagnostic
172 of the presence of a well-developed DCM, generally associated with stratified and nutrient-
173 depleted waters in the upper photic zone. This view is corroborated by recent surface water
174 and sediment-trap studies on coccolithophore distribution and export production in the
175 EMED [Malinverno et al., 2003, 2009].

176 [14] These ecological features make *F. profunda* particularly well suited to document
177 temporal changes in the development of the DCM and to qualitatively infer the depth of the
178 nutricline [Okada and Honjo, 1973; Molfino and McIntyre, 1990; Castradori, 1993; Beaufort
179 et al., 1997]. In addition, relative abundances of *F. profunda* increase (decrease) when the
180 upper photic zone is impoverished (replenished) in nutrients [Beaufort et al., 1997; Incarbona
181 et al., 2008]. We reconstruct past dynamics of the nutricline within the photic zone in the
182 southeastern Aegean Sea from down-core records of *F. profunda* percentages. Additional
183 support to this reconstruction is provided by mapping the distribution of *F. profunda* in the
184 EMED surface sediments at several locations (Figure 2A), for which modern (satellite-
185 derived) estimates of Chl-a concentrations at the sea surface are available (Figure 2B).

186 [15] A second species we focus on is *Helicosphaera carteri*, which is considered as a
187 coastal taxon, indicative of moderately elevated nutrient conditions and turbidity [Giraudeau,
188 1992; Ziveri et al., 1995, 2000; Colmenero-Hidalgo et al., 2004; Ziveri et al., 2004;

189 *Malinverno et al.*, 2009]. Previous work has attributed high abundances of *H. carteri* to
190 fresher and probably more turbid surface waters in the Alboran Sea [*Colmenero-Hidalgo et*
191 *al.*, 2004] and the Adriatic Sea (during S5) [*Narciso et al.*, 2010].

192

193 **5. Results**

194 **5.1. Proxy validation: relative abundances of *F. profunda* in the central and** 195 **eastern Mediterranean Sea versus Chl-a concentrations**

196 [16] In surface samples from the central and eastern Mediterranean Sea, the relative
197 abundances of *F. profunda* range between 0.20% and 38.15% (N= 124, average = 11.86, σ =
198 7.27) (Figure 2A). *Florisphaera profunda* percentages remain generally in the same order of
199 magnitude throughout the study area with the exception of the southern Aegean Sea and
200 offshore Libya, where values are lower due to shallower water depth (Figure 2A), in line with
201 previous studies [*Incarbona et al.*, 2008]. We note an exponential anticorrelation *between F.*
202 *profunda* percentages and surface water Chl-a concentrations (Figure 2C) throughout the
203 EMED:

$$204 \quad \text{Chl-a} = -0.041 \times \ln(\% F. profunda) + 0.196 \quad (R^2 = 0.70, N = 24, \sigma = 0.018) \quad (1)$$

205 This supports previous studies carried out in the Mediterranean Sea [*Incarbona et al.*, 2008]
206 as well as in other regions of the world ocean [*Beaufort et al.*, 1997, 2001, 2003], pointing to
207 an exponential increase of *F. profunda* percentages when primary productivity of the surface
208 waters decreases, or – in other words – when the locus of productivity shifts to subsurface.

209

210 **5.2. The LC21 downcore record**

211 [17] Figure 3 shows our downcore coccolith records in LC21 along with other previously
212 reported geochemical and sedimentary data from the same site [Marino *et al.*, 2007].
213 *Florisphaera profunda* percentages exhibit relatively low values in the pre- and post-sapropel
214 sections (<20%), an abrupt increase up to ~58% prior to the onset of the anoxic
215 sedimentation, and values between 20 and 38% (the latter value corresponding to a distinct
216 peak at ~122.2 ka BP) throughout the remainder of the sapropel event (Figure 3A). The LC21
217 *H. carteri* percentages likewise display higher values during the sapropel event and lower
218 values before and after S5 (Figure 3B). After an abrupt increase roughly coincident with the
219 aforementioned *F. profunda* peak, the S5 is characterized by a long-term decrease punctuated
220 by several short-term peaks, to eventually reach pre-sapropel values in step with the cessation
221 of the anoxic sedimentation. The absolute abundance of coccoliths (Figure 3A) displays
222 opposing patterns with respect to both *F. profunda* and *H. carteri* profiles in that it is higher
223 in the non-sapropel intervals and lower during S5.

224

225 6. Discussion

226 [18] The high *F. profunda* percentages within sapropel S5 in southeastern Aegean core
227 LC21 (Figure 3A) agree with previous observations of enhanced abundances of this taxon in
228 several eastern Mediterranean sapropels, relative to non-sapropel intervals [Castradori, 1993;
229 Negri *et al.*, 1999; Triantaphyllou *et al.*, 2010; Incarbona *et al.*, 2011]. The evidence from
230 LC21 supports the initial foraminifer-based hypothesis of a strong DCM during the
231 intensively developed sapropel S5 [Rohling and Gieskes, 1989], as opposed to generally
232 productive conditions in the upper photic zone. The co-registered nature and the high
233 temporal resolution of the LC21 records allow unambiguous documentation of the timing
234 relationships between freshwater-bound hydrographic changes in the upper water column,

235 development of the DCM and onset of the organic-rich sedimentation in the southeastern
236 Aegean Sea.

237

238 **6.1. Freshwater flooding, development of the DCM and dynamics of the** 239 **nutricline**

240 [19] The LC21 records reveal that the abrupt increase of *F. profunda* and *H. carteri*
241 percentages and the decrease in the total coccolith abundances at ~124 ka coincides with the
242 first half of the ~1.7‰ decrease in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ (Figure 3C), which preceded by a few decades
243 [Marino *et al.*, 2007] the onset of the C_{org} deposition at the same site (Figure 3D). The
244 negative $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ shift testifies to pronounced sea surface freshening prior to S5 deposition
245 [Marino *et al.*, 2007], while the prominent *F. profunda* peak marks the development of a
246 productive DCM in the subsurface. The remarkable synchronicity (within the multi-decadal
247 resolution of the records) of these changes highlights a strong coupling between freshwater-
248 bound hydrographic changes at the sea surface and subsurface productivity increase in the
249 southeastern Aegean Sea. A sharp reduction of the surface buoyancy loss likely reduced deep
250 convective mixing and amplified vertical stratification between surface and subsurface
251 waters, as exemplified by steep oxygen isotope gradients ($\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$, Figure 3E) between
252 subsurface-dwelling *Neogloboquadrina pachyderma* (dextral) (Figure 3F) and surface-
253 dwelling *Globigerinoides ruber* (Figure 3C) [cf., Rohling *et al.*, 2004, 2006].

254 [20] It has been suggested that these developments caused the LIW to shoal [Rohling,
255 1994; Myers *et al.*, 1998; Rohling *et al.*, 2006], promoting enhanced upward advection of
256 nutrients [Rohling and Gieskes, 1989] that fuelled a productive DCM below a strong salinity
257 gradient (halocline). Nutrient utilization within the DCM and the virtual absence of mixing in
258 the upper water column [Rohling *et al.*, 2006; Marino *et al.*, 2007] would nutrient-starve the

259 surface system above it [Sachs and Repeta, 1999], consistent with the drop in overall
260 coccolith concentrations in our records. Additional insights into the depth of the DCM prior
261 to S5 deposition in LC21 are provided by the contemporaneous increase of *H. carteri*, which
262 suggests increased turbidity of surface waters at this location. This would have inhibited light
263 penetration (hence photosynthesis) at depth, implying that the nutricline was positioned in the
264 subsurface yet at relatively shallow levels in the photic layer.

265 [21] The sharp C_{org} increase to values higher than 13% at ~123.3 coincided with an
266 expansion of euxinic conditions from the bottom to ~200 m depth and with the accumulation
267 of respiration products at the base of the photic zone (very low $\delta^{13}C_{pachyderma}$ in Figure 3G)
268 [Marino *et al.*, 2007]. Oxygen-starved conditions would have promoted extensive
269 denitrification [Krom *et al.*, 2010] and phosphorous regeneration [Slomp *et al.*, 2002], thereby
270 enhancing the nutrient availability within the water column. It seems therefore surprising that
271 the *F. profunda* percentages decreased considerably at 123.3 ka and remained generally low
272 throughout S5 (yet still higher by ~15% than in non-S5 intervals). There is a possibility that
273 during S5 the DCM was dominated by phytoplankton groups other than coccoliths, e.g.,
274 diatoms [Kemp *et al.*, 1999]. This is supported by the low coccolith concentrations in LC21
275 (Figure 3A) and would also agree with the lowered $CaCO_3$ levels generally found in EMED
276 sapropels [Van Os *et al.*, 1994; Reitz and de Lange, 2006]. Alternatively, the sharp reduction
277 of the vertical stratification (erosion of the halocline) that we observe at ~123.3 (low $\Delta\delta^{18}O$,
278 Figure 3E), via downward diffusive mixing [Casford *et al.*, 2002] of the freshening signal
279 (low *N. pachyderma* $\delta^{18}O$, Figure 3F) may have inhibited the concentration of nutrients near
280 the base of the photic zone and, in turn, decreased productivity within the DCM.

281 [22] The very low percentages of *F. profunda* and high coccolith concentrations (Figure
282 3A) in the non-S5 sections point to an oligotrophic photic zone with most of the primary
283 production focused within its upper part. During both the pre- and post S5 intervals, and

284 similar to the present day EMED, the upper water column was homogenized (low $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$),
285 with well-ventilated subthermocline waters [Pierre, 1999; Rohling et al., 2006]. The
286 nutricline likely was positioned below the photic zone with the surface primary productivity
287 resulting, from upward mixing and entrainment of thermocline waters during the winter
288 season [Krom et al., 2003]. At ~119 ka the *N. pachyderma* $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ decreased, in apparent
289 disagreement with the proposed return to pre-S5 conditions. This may be explained by
290 upward admixture of old deep waters, laden with isotopically light (respired) CO_2 , due to the
291 resumption of deep-water formation. It is interesting that, although these developments would
292 have presumably lifted remineralized nutrients towards the photic zone [Stratford and
293 Haines, 2002], the low *F. profunda* percentages suggest no productivity increase in the DCM
294 during this period. This evidence emphasizes that the freshwater-induced shoaling of the
295 pycnocline and the development of a distinct halocline underneath a freshened surface layer
296 are fundamental ingredients to develop a nutrient-replete DCM while the sea surface
297 experiences nutrient-starvation.

298

299 **6.2. Impacts of the hydrographic and productivity changes on the** 300 **development of anoxic conditions in the eastern Mediterranean Sea**

301 [23] The LC21 records presented here provide the first direct evidence that, prior to the
302 deposition of the last interglacial sapropel S5, the nutricline abruptly (within less than a
303 century) shoaled within the photic layer and that this change occurred in concert with a series
304 of major hydrographic reorganizations initiated by massive [Rohling et al., 2002] monsoon-
305 fuelled freshwater discharge along the North African margin [Rohling et al., 2002; Osborne
306 et al., 2008, 2010]. Two additional lines of evidence support the tight coupling between
307 freshwater perturbation in the EMED and the vertical migration of the nutricline in the upper
308 water column. First, the distinct increase of *F. profunda* percentages at ~122.2 ka BP in LC21

309 (see Figure S1 in the auxiliary material) coincides with the reactivation of the excess
310 monsoon discharge route through the Libyan Sahara [Osborne *et al.*, 2008] into the EMED
311 [Rohling *et al.*, 2002]. Second, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ and *F. profunda* percentages strongly covary in
312 LC21 (Figure 4). Accordingly, curtailment of the EMED deep ventilation [Marino *et al.*,
313 2007] and increased productivity in the DCM (this study) can both be seen as abrupt
314 responses of the EMED thermohaline cells and of the vertical flux of nutrients (and their
315 subsequent utilization) to the orbitally driven [Revel *et al.*, 2010; Ziegler *et al.*, 2010]
316 monsoon floods.

317 [24] The enhanced C_{org} preservation promoted by seafloor anoxia is unlikely to account
318 alone for the abrupt transition from C_{org} -depleted to C_{org} -enriched sediments in the EMED, let
319 alone for the remarkably high C_{org} levels (up to ~14%) found in the southeastern Aegean
320 sediments during S5 (Figure 3D) [Marino *et al.*, 2007]. The particularly high C_{org} values in
321 LC21 and at other locations throughout the EMED during S5 [Struck *et al.*, 2001; Rohling *et*
322 *al.*, 2006] are contrasted with moderate C_{org} levels (~2-3%) found in the Aegean Sea
323 [Mercone *et al.*, 2001; Thomson *et al.*, 2004] and in the EMED [De Lange *et al.*, 2008]
324 during S1 and in other Late Pleistocene sapropels [Kallel *et al.*, 2000]. We suggest that the
325 elevated C_{org} levels of the last interglacial sapropel event require a concomitant increase in
326 the export flux of organic matter to the sea floor. Reconstruction based on coccoliths (this
327 study) and on diatoms [Kemp *et al.*, 1999] prove that prior to and during S5 deposition, an
328 increased C_{org} export to the deep sea likely resulted from the development of a productive
329 DCM in the EMED subsurface. By contrast, the weakly developed S1 features lower *F.*
330 *profunda* percentages [Negri *et al.*, 1999; Thomson *et al.*, 2004; Triantaphyllou *et al.*, 2009]
331 and a lack of diatoms [Boere *et al.*, 2011]. Hence, the amount of freshwater discharged and
332 its associated hydrographic changes, together with the advection across the upper water
333 column of nutrients that are regenerated under oxygen-starved conditions [Slomp *et al.*, 2002;

334 *Krom et al.*, 2010], modulate the magnitude of C_{org} burial in the EMED sediments during
335 sapropel formation.

336

337 **7. Conclusions**

338 [25] We present new coccolith records (*F. profunda* and *H. carteri* percentages,
339 coccolith concentrations) that document in high temporal detail the primary productivity and
340 turbidity changes prior to, during, and after the deposition of the last interglacial sapropel S5
341 in the southeastern Aegean Sea core LC21. The (negative) exponential relationship between
342 *F. profunda* percentages and satellite-derived Chl-a concentrations at 24 locations in the
343 EMED supports the employment of downcore relative abundances of this taxon to reconstruct
344 past productivity patterns in LC21.

345 [26] Comparison of our coccolith records with the co-registered planktonic foraminiferal
346 stable isotopes from the southeastern Aegean Sea reveals that the onset of the sea surface
347 freshening prior to S5 deposition [*Marino et al.*, 2007] was accompanied by an abrupt shift
348 towards higher turbidity and lower primary productivity conditions in the surface waters,
349 while a productive DCM developed in the subsurface. The remarkable synchronicity of these
350 developments points to a strong sensitivity and instantaneous response (within less than a
351 century) of the vertical fluxes and utilization of nutrients to freshwater perturbation in the
352 EMED. Specifically, the onset of major monsoon-fuelled freshwater flooding within the last
353 interglacial period [*Rohling et al.*, 2002, 2004] initiated a series of hydrographic adjustments
354 that rapidly culminated in the isolation of a nutrient-starved surface layer from a nutrient-
355 replete DCM.

356 [27] We speculate that the permanent cyclonic circulation at the core LC21 site and the
357 associated “doming” of the isopycnals caused the nutricline to shoal well within the photic

358 layer during the S5. This fuelled a DCM that was possibly more productive than in other
359 sectors of the EMED featuring different circulation regimes (e.g., close to anticyclonic
360 gyres), thereby (partly) explaining the very low subsurface $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values and the rapid upward
361 progression of the euxinic conditions previously documented in LC21 [*Marino et al.*, 2007].
362 These features agree well with the enhanced denitrification in the water column [*Krom et al.*,
363 2010] and sediments and with the phosphorus recycling [*Slomp et al.*, 2002] proposed for the
364 EMED during sapropel formation.

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381 **References cited**

- 382 Baith, K., R. Lindsay, and G. Fu (2001), Data analysis system developed for ocean color satellite
383 sensors, *EOS Trans. AGU*, 82(18).
- 384 Bar-Matthews, M., A. Ayalon, and A. Kaufman (2000), Timing and hydrological conditions of Sapropel
385 events in the Eastern Mediterranean, as evident from speleothems, Soreq cave, Israel, *Chemical*
386 *Geology*, 169(1-2), 145-156.
- 387 Beaufort, L., Y. Lancelot, P. Camberlin, O. Cayre, E. Vincent, F. Bassinot, and L. Labeyrie (1997),
388 Insolation cycles as a major control of equatorial Indian Ocean primary production, *Science*,
389 278(5342), 1451-1454.
- 390 Beaufort, L., T. de Garidel-Thoron, A. C. Mix, and N. G. Piasis (2001), ENSO-like forcing on oceanic
391 primary production during the Late Pleistocene, *Science*, 293(5539), 2440-2444.
- 392 Beaufort, L., T. de Garidel-Thoron, B. Linsley, D. Oppo, and N. Buchet (2003), Biomass burning and
393 oceanic primary production estimates in the Sulu Sea area over the last 380 kyr and the East
394 Asian monsoon dynamics, *Marine Geology*, 201(1-3), 53-65.
- 395 Boere, A. C., W. I. C. Rijpstra, G. J. De Lange, J. S. Sinninghe Damsté, and M. J. L. Coolen (2011),
396 Preservation potential of ancient plankton DNA in Pleistocene marine sediments, *Geobiology*,
397 9(5), 377-393. doi: 10.1111/j.1472-4669.2011.00290.x.
- 398 Calvert, S. E., B. Nielsen, and M. R. Fontugne (1992), Evidence from nitrogen isotope ratios for
399 enhanced productivity during formation of Eastern Mediterranean sapropels, *Nature*, 359(6392),
400 223-225.
- 401 Casford, J. S. L., E. J. Rohling, R. Abu-Zied, S. Cooke, C. Fontanier, M. Leng, and V. Lykousis (2002),
402 Circulation changes and nutrient concentrations in the late Quaternary Aegean Sea: A nonsteady
403 state concept for sapropel formation, *Paleoceanography*, 17(2), 1024. doi:
404 10.1029/2000pa000601.

405 Casford, J. S. L., E. J. Rohling, R. H. Abu-Zied, C. Fontanier, F. J. Jorissen, M. J. Leng, G. Schmiedl, and J.
406 Thomson (2003), A dynamic concept for eastern Mediterranean circulation and oxygenation
407 during sapropel formation, *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 190, 103-119.

408 Castradori, D. (1993), Calcareous Nannofossils and the Origin of Eastern Mediterranean Sapropels,
409 *Paleoceanography*, 8(4), 459-471.

410 Colmenero-Hidalgo, E., J.-A. Flores, F. J. Sierro, M. Á. Bárcena, L. Löwemark, J. Schönfeld, and J. O.
411 Grimalt (2004), Ocean surface water response to short-term climate changes revealed by
412 coccolithophores from the Gulf of Cadiz (NE Atlantic) and Alboran Sea (W Mediterranean),
413 *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 205(3-4), 317-336.

414 Cramp, A., and G. O'Sullivan (1999), Neogene sapropels in the Mediterranean: a review, *Marine*
415 *Geology*, 153(1-4), 11-28.

416 D'Ortenzio, F., and M. Ribera d'Alcalà (2009), On the trophic regimes of the Mediterranean Sea: a
417 satellite analysis, *Biogeosciences*, 6(2), 139-148.

418 De Lange, G. J., and H. L. ten Haven (1983), Recent sapropel formation in the eastern Mediterranean,
419 *Nature*, 305(5937), 797-798.

420 De Lange, G. J., J. Thomson, A. Reitz, C. P. Slomp, M. Speranza Principato, E. Erba, and C. Corselli
421 (2008), Synchronous basin-wide formation and redox-controlled preservation of a
422 Mediterranean sapropel, *Nature Geosci*, 1(9), 606-610.

423 Feldman, G. C., and C. R. McClain (2011), Ocean Color Web, CZCS, OCTS and SeaWiFS Reprocessing 5,
424 edited by N. Kuring, Bailey, S. W., NASA Goddard Space Flight Center.

425 Giraudeau, J. (1992), Distribution of Recent Nannofossils beneath the Benguela System - Southwest
426 African Continental-Margin, *Marine Geology*, 108(2), 219-237.

427 Hecht, A., N. Pinardi, and A. R. Robinson (1988), Currents, Water Masses, Eddies and Jets in the
428 Mediterranean Levantine Basin, *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 18(10), 1320-1353. doi:
429 10.1175/1520-0485(1988).

430 Hecht, A., and I. Gertman (2001), Physical features of the eastern Mediterranean resulting from the
431 integration of POEM data with Russian Mediterranean Cruises, *Deep Sea Research Part I:
432 Oceanographic Research Papers*, 48(8), 1847-1876.

433 Honjo, S., and H. Okada (1974), Community structure of coccolithophores in the photic layer of the
434 mid-Pacific, *Micropaleontology*, 20(2), 209-230.

435 Ignatiades, L., O. Gotsis-Skretas, K. Pagou, and E. Krasakopoulou (2009), Diversification of
436 phytoplankton community structure and related parameters along a large-scale longitudinal
437 east-west transect of the Mediterranean Sea, *J. Plankton Res.*, 31(4), 411-428. doi:
438 10.1093/plankt/fbn124.

439 Incarbona, A., S. Bonomo, E. Di Stefano, S. Zgozi, N. Essarbout, M. Talha, G. Tranchida, A. Bonanno,
440 B. Patti, F. Placenti, G. Buscaino, A. Cuttitta, G. Basilone, T. Bahri, F. Massa, P. Censi, and S.
441 Mazzola (2008), Calcareous nannofossil surface sediment assemblages from the Sicily Channel
442 (central Mediterranean Sea): Palaeoceanographic implications, *Marine Micropaleontology*, 67(3-
443 4), 297-309.

444 Incarbona, A., P. Ziveri, N. Sabatino, D. S. Manta, and M. Sprovieri (2011), Conflicting
445 coccolithophore and geochemical evidence for productivity levels in the Eastern Mediterranean
446 sapropel S1, *Marine Micropaleontology*, 81(3-4), 131-143. doi: 10.1016/j.marmicro.2011.09.003.

447 Kallel, N., J. C. Duplessy, L. Labeyrie, M. Fontugne, M. Paterne, and M. Montacer (2000),
448 Mediterranean pluvial periods and sapropel formation over the last 200 000 years,
449 *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 157(1-2), 45-58.

450 Kemp, A. E. S., R. B. Pearce, I. Koizumi, J. Pike, and S. J. Rance (1999), The role of mat-forming
451 diatoms in the formation of Mediterranean sapropels *Nature*, 399(6731), 84-84.

452 Knappertsbusch, M. (1993), Geographic distribution of living and Holocene coccolithophores in the
453 Mediterranean Sea, *Marine Micropaleontology*, 21(1-3), 219-247.

454 Krom, M. D., N. Kress, S. Brenner, and L. I. Gordon (1991), Phosphorus limitation of primary
455 production in the eastern Mediterranean Sea, *Limnol. Oceanogr.*, 36, 424-432.

456 Krom, M. D., S. Brenner, N. Kress, A. Neori, and L. I. Gordon (1992), Nutrient dynamics and new
457 production in a warm-core eddy from the Eastern Mediterranean Sea, *Deep Sea Research Part A*.
458 *Oceanographic Research Papers*, 39(3-4), 467-480.

459 Krom, M. D., S. Groom, and T. Zohary (2003), The Eastern Mediterranean, in *Biogeochemistry of*
460 *marine systems*, edited, pp. 91-126, Blackwell/CRC Press.

461 Krom, M. D., K. C. Emeis, and P. Van Cappellen (2010), Why is the Eastern Mediterranean
462 phosphorus limited?, *Prog. Oceanogr.*, 85(3-4), 236-244.

463 Lototskaya, A., P. Ziveri, G. M. Ganssen, and J. E. van Hinte (1998), Calcareous nannofloral response
464 to Termination II at 45°N, 25°W (northeast Atlantic), *Marine Micropaleontology*, 34(1-2), 47-70.

465 Malanotte-Rizzoli, P., and A. Hecht (1988), Large-scale properties of the Eastern Mediterranean: A
466 review, *Oceanol. Acta*, 11(4), 323-335.

467 Malinverno, E. (2000), *Ecologia, produttività e distribuzione verticale dei coccolitoforidi nel Mar*
468 *Ionio (Mediterraneo Orientale) nell'autunno 1997*, 434 pp, Università Milano-Bicocca, Milano.

469 Malinverno, E., P. Ziveri, and C. Corselli (2003), Coccolithophorid distribution in the Ionian Sea and its
470 relationship to eastern Mediterranean circulation during late fall to early winter 1997, *J.*
471 *Geophys. Res.-Oceans*, 108 (C9), 8115, doi: 8110.1029/2002JC001346.

472 Malinverno, E., M. V. Triantaphyllou, S. Stavrakakis, P. Ziveri, and V. Lykousis (2009), Seasonal and
473 spatial variability of coccolithophore export production at the South-Western margin of Crete
474 (Eastern Mediterranean), *Marine Micropaleontology*, 71(3-4), 131-147.

475 Marino, G., E. J. Rohling, W. I. C. Rijpstra, F. Sangiorgi, S. Schouten, and J. S. S. Damsté (2007),
476 Aegean Sea as driver of hydrographic and ecological changes in the eastern Mediterranean,
477 *Geology*, 35(8), 675-678. doi: 10.1130/g23831a.1.

478 Marino, G., E. J. Rohling, F. Sangiorgi, A. Hayes, J. L. Casford, A. F. Lotter, M. Kucera, and H. Brinkhuis
479 (2009), Early and middle Holocene in the Aegean Sea: interplay between high and low latitude
480 climate variability, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 28(27-28), 3246-3262.

481 Matsuoka, H., and H. Okada (1989), Quantitative analysis of quaternary nanoplankton in the
482 subtropical northwestern Pacific Ocean, *Marine Micropaleontology*, 14(1-3), 97-118.

483 Mercone, D., J. Thomson, R. H. Abu-Zied, I. W. Croudace, and E. J. Rohling (2001), High-resolution
484 geochemical and micropalaeontological profiling of the most recent eastern Mediterranean
485 sapropel, *Marine Geology*, 177(1-2), 25-44.

486 Molfino, B., and A. McIntyre (1990), Precessional Forcing of Nutricline Dynamics in the Equatorial
487 Atlantic, *Science*, 249(4970), 766-769.

488 Myers, P. G., K. Haines, and E. J. Rohling (1998), Modeling the Paleocirculation of the Mediterranean:
489 The Last Glacial Maximum and the Holocene with Emphasis on the Formation of Sapropel S1,
490 *Paleoceanography*, 13(6), 586-606. doi: 10.1029/98pa02736.

491 Narciso, À., J.-A. Flores, M. Cachão, F. J. Sierro, E. Colmenero-Hidalgo, A. Piva, and A. Asoli (2010),
492 Sea surface dynamics and coccolithophore behaviour during sapropel deposition of Marine
493 Isotope Stage 7, 6 and 5 in the Western Adriatic sea, *Revista Española de Micropaleontología*,
494 42(3), 345-358.

495 Negri, A., L. Capotondi, and J. Keller (1999), Calcareous nanofossils, planktonic foraminifera and
496 oxygen isotopes in the late Quaternary sapropels of the Ionian Sea, *Marine Geology*, 157(1-2),
497 89-103.

498 Negri, A., A. Ferretti, T. Wagner, and P. A. Meyers (2009), Phanerozoic organic-carbon-rich marine
499 sediments: Overview and future research challenges, *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology*,
500 *Palaeoecology*, 273(3-4), 218-227.

501 Okada, H., and S. Honjo (1973), The distribution of oceanic coccolithophorids in the Pacific, *Deep-Sea*
502 *Research Part I-Oceanographic Research Papers*, 20, 355-374.

503 Okada, H., and A. McIntyre (1977), Modern coccolithophores of the Pacific and North Atlantic
504 oceans, *Micropaleontology*, 23(1), 1-54.

505 Osborne, A. H., D. Vance, E. J. Rohling, N. Barton, M. Rogerson, and N. Fello (2008), A humid corridor
506 across the Sahara for the migration of early modern humans out of Africa 120,000 years ago,

507 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 105(43), 16444-16447. doi:
508 10.1073/pnas.0804472105.

509 Osborne, A. H., G. Marino, D. Vance, and E. J. Rohling (2010), Eastern Mediterranean surface water
510 Nd during Eemian sapropel S5: monitoring northerly (mid-latitude) versus southerly (sub-
511 tropical) freshwater contributions, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 29(19-20), 2473-2483.

512 Passier, H. F., H.-J. Bosch, I. A. Nijenhuis, L. J. Lourens, M. E. Bottcher, A. Leenders, J. S. S. Damste, G.
513 J. de Lange, and J. W. Leeuw (1999), Sulphidic Mediterranean surface waters during Pliocene
514 sapropel formation, *Nature*, 397(6715), 146-149.

515 Pierre, C. (1999), The oxygen and carbon isotope distribution in the Mediterranean water masses,
516 *Marine Geology*, 153(1-4), 41-45.

517 Pinardi, N., and E. Masetti (2000), Variability of the large scale general circulation of the
518 Mediterranean Sea from observations and modelling: a review, *Palaeogeography,*
519 *Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 158(3-4), 153-173.

520 Reitz, A., and G. J. de Lange (2006), Abundant Sr-rich aragonite in eastern Mediterranean sapropel
521 S1: Diagenetic vs. detrital/biogenic origin, *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology,*
522 235(1-3), 135-148.

523 Revel, M., E. Ducassou, F. E. Grousset, S. M. Bernasconi, S. Migeon, S. Revillon, J. Mascle, A. Murat, S.
524 Zaragosi, and D. Bosch (2010), 100,000 Years of African monsoon variability recorded in
525 sediments of the Nile margin, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 29(11-12), 1342-1362.

526 Rohling, E. J., and W. W. C. Gieskes (1989), Late Quaternary changes in Mediterranean intermediate
527 water density and formation rate, *Paleoceanography*, 4(5), 531-545.

528 Rohling, E. J., and H. L. Bryden (1992), Man-Induced Salinity and Temperature Increases in Western
529 Mediterranean Deep Water, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 97(C7), 11191-11198. doi: 10.1029/92jc00767.

530 Rohling, E. J. (1994), Review and new aspects concerning the formation of eastern Mediterranean
531 sapropels, *Marine Geology*, 122(1-2), 1-28.

532 Rohling, E. J., T. R. Cane, S. Cooke, M. Sprovieri, I. Bouloubassi, K. C. Emeis, R. Schiebel, D. Kroon, F. J.
533 Jorissen, A. Lorre, and A. E. S. Kemp (2002), African monsoon variability during the previous
534 interglacial maximum, *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 202(1), 61-75.

535 Rohling, E. J., M. Sprovieri, T. Cane, J. S. L. Casford, S. Cooke, I. Bouloubassi, K. C. Emeis, R. Schiebel,
536 M. Rogerson, A. Hayes, F. J. Jorissen, and D. Kroon (2004), Reconstructing past planktic
537 foraminiferal habitats using stable isotope data: a case history for Mediterranean sapropel S5,
538 *Marine Micropaleontology*, 50(1-2), 89-123.

539 Rohling, E. J., E. C. Hopmans, and J. S. Sinninghe Damsté (2006), Water column dynamics during the
540 last interglacial anoxic event in the Mediterranean (sapropel S5), *Paleoceanography*, 21(2),
541 PA2018. doi: 10.1029/2005pa001237.

542 Rossignol-Strick, M., W. Nesteroff, P. Olive, and C. Vergnaud-Grazzini (1982), After the deluge:
543 Mediterranean stagnation and sapropel formation, *Nature*, 295(5845), 105-110.

544 Rothwell, R. G. (1995), Marion Dufresne Cruise report - Mediterranean giant piston coring transect.
545 17th January-9th February. Marseille, France - Limassol, Cyprus. Southampton Oceanography
546 Centre, 77 pp. and appendices (unpubl. manuscript).

547 Sachs, J. P., and D. J. Repeta (1999), Oligotrophy and Nitrogen Fixation During Eastern
548 Mediterranean Sapropel Events, *Science*, 286(5449), 2485-2488. doi:
549 10.1126/science.286.5449.2485.

550 Sarmiento, J. L., T. Herbert, and J. R. Toggweiler (1988), Mediterranean nutrient balance and
551 episodes of anoxia, *Glob. Biogeochem. Cycle*, 2(4), 427-444.

552 Siokou-Frangou, I., U. Christaki, M. G. Mazzocchi, M. Montresor, M. Ribera d'Alcalá, D. Vaqué, and A.
553 Zingone (2010), Plankton in the open Mediterranean Sea: a review, *Biogeosciences*, 7(5), 1543.
554 doi: 10.5194/bg-7-1543-2010.

555 Slomp, C. P., J. Thomson, and G. J. de Lange (2002), Enhanced regeneration of phosphorus during
556 formation of the most recent eastern Mediterranean sapropel (S1), *Geochimica et Cosmochimica*
557 *Acta*, 66(7), 1171-1184.

558 Stratford, K., and K. Haines (2002), Modeling nutrient cycling during the eastern Mediterranean
559 transient event 1987-1995 and beyond, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 29(3), 1035. doi:
560 10.1029/2001gl013559.

561 Struck, U., K.-C. Emeis, M. Voß, M. D. Krom, and G. H. Rau (2001), Biological productivity during
562 sapropel S5 formation in the Eastern Mediterranean Sea: evidence from stable isotopes of
563 nitrogen and carbon, *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 65(19), 3249-3266.

564 Theocharis, A., E. Balopoulos, S. Kioroglou, H. Kontoyiannis, and A. Iona (1999), A synthesis of the
565 circulation and hydrography of the South Aegean Sea and the Straits of the Cretan Arc (March
566 1994-January 1995), *Prog. Oceanogr.*, 44(4), 469-509.

567 Thomson, J., D. Crudeli, G. J. de Lange, C. P. Slomp, E. Erba, C. Corselli, and S. E. Calvert (2004),
568 *Florisphaera profunda* and the origin and diagenesis of carbonate phases in eastern
569 Mediterranean sapropel units, *Paleoceanography*, 19(3), PA3003. doi: 10.1029/2003pa000976.

570 Triantaphyllou, M., A. Antonarakou, K. Kouli, M. Dimiza, G. Kontakiotis, M. Papanikolaou, P. Ziveri, P.
571 Mortyn, V. Lianou, V. Lykousis, and M. Dermitzakis (2009), Late Glacial–Holocene
572 ecostratigraphy of the south-eastern Aegean Sea, based on plankton and pollen assemblages,
573 *Geo-Marine Letters*, 29(4), 249-267. doi: 10.1007/s00367-009-0139-5.

574 Triantaphyllou, M., A. Antonarakou, M. Dimiza, and C. Anagnostou (2010), Calcareous nannofossil
575 and planktonic foraminiferal distributional patterns during deposition of sapropels S6, S5 and S1
576 in the Libyan Sea (Eastern Mediterranean), *Geo-Marine Letters*, 30(1), 1-13. doi:
577 10.1007/s00367-009-0145-7.

578 Turley, C. M., M. Bianchi, U. Christaki, P. Conan, J. R. W. Harris, S. Psarra, G. Ruddy, E. D. Stutt, A.
579 Tselepidis, and F. V. Wambeke (2000), Relationship between primary producers and bacteria in
580 an oligotrophic sea - the Mediterranean and biogeochemical implications, *Marine Ecology*
581 *Progress Series*, 193, 11-18. doi: 10.3354/meps193011.

582 Ujiie, H., Y. Tanaka, and T. Ono (1991), Late Quarternary paleoceanographic record from the middle
583 Ryukyu Trench slope, northwest Pacific, *Marine Micropaleontology*, 18(1-2), 115-128.

584 Van Os, B. J. H., L. J. Lourens, F. J. Hilgen, G. J. De Lange, and L. Beaufort (1994), The Formation of
585 Pliocene Sapropels and Carbonate Cycles in the Mediterranean: Diagenesis, Dilution, and
586 Productivity, *Paleoceanography*, 9(4), 601-617. doi: 10.1029/94pa00597.

587 Wu, P., and K. Haines (1996), Modeling the dispersal of Levantine Intermediate Water and its role in
588 Mediterranean deep water formation, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 101(C3), 6591-6607. doi:
589 10.1029/95jc03555.

590 Wüst, G. (1961), On the vertical circulation of the Mediterranean Sea, *Journal of Geophysical*
591 *Research*, 66, 3261-3271.

592 Yilmaz, A., and S. Tuğrul (1998), The effect of cold- and warm-core eddies on the distribution and
593 stoichiometry of dissolved nutrients in the northeastern Mediterranean, *Journal of Marine*
594 *Systems*, 16(3-4), 253-268.

595 Zavattarielli, M., and G. L. Mellor (1995), A Numerical Study of the Mediterranean Sea Circulation,
596 *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 25(6), 1384-1414. doi: 10.1175/1520-0485(1995).

597 Zervakis, V., D. Georgopoulos, and P. G. Drakopoulos (2000), The role of the North Aegean in
598 triggering the recent Eastern Mediterranean climatic changes, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 105(C11), 26103-
599 26116. doi: 10.1029/2000jc900131.

600 Ziegler, M., E. Tuenter, and L. J. Lourens (2010), The precession phase of the boreal summer
601 monsoon as viewed from the eastern Mediterranean (ODP Site 968), *Quaternary Science*
602 *Reviews*, 29(11-12), 1481-1490.

603 Ziveri, P., R. C. Thunell, and D. Rio (1995), Export Production of Coccolithophores in an Upwelling
604 Region - Results from San-Pedro Basin, Southern California Borderlands, *Marine*
605 *Micropaleontology*, 24(3-4), 335-358.

606 Ziveri, P., A. Rutten, G. J. de Lange, J. Thomson, and C. Corselli (2000), Present-day coccolith fluxes
607 recorded in central eastern Mediterranean sediment traps and surface sediments,
608 *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 158(3-4), 175-195.

609 Ziveri, P., K. H. Baumann, B. Bockel, J. Bollmann, and J. R. Young (2004), Biogeography of selected
610 Holocene coccoliths in the Atlantic Ocean, in *Coccolithophores: From Molecular Processes to*
611 *Global Impact*, edited by H. R. Thierstein and J. R. Young, pp. 403-428.

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614

615 **Figure captions**

616 **Figure 1:** Map of the Mediterranean Sea showing the main patterns of surface water
617 circulation [Pinardi and Masetti, 2000], blue arrows; and location of deep water formation
618 sites, red areas. The red star indicates the location of core LC-21. Red, white and grey circles
619 show the location of the surface sediment samples that were used for the distribution of *F.*
620 *profunda* in figure 2A and the reconstructions presented in figure 2C. The black circles depict
621 the location of the surface sediment samples only used for the distribution of *F. profunda* in
622 figure 2A. A complete list of these samples is given in table S1 in the auxiliary material.

623

624 **Figure 2:** A) Distribution map of the relative abundances of *F. profunda* in the surface
625 sediment of the central and eastern Mediterranean Sea. B) Distribution map of the averaged
626 concentration of chlorophyll a (Chl-a) extracted from satellite imagery between 1996 and
627 2006 [Feldman and McClain, 2011]. The symbols are the same as in Figure 1. C) Relation
628 between the relative abundances of *F. profunda* and the surface concentration of Chl-a at the
629 different sites: white circles, samples of the Sicily Strait [Incarbona et al., 2008], grey circles,
630 samples offshore Libya [Incarbona et al., 2008]; and red circles, samples of the open eastern
631 Mediterranean and southern Aegean Seas. The heavy black, grey and red lines depict the
632 logarithmic regressions and the red dotted lines depict the 95% interval of confidence of our
633 estimation, which takes into account for the respective uncertainties characterizing the Chl-a

634 concentrations and the relative abundances of *F. profunda*. The vertical error bars correspond
635 to 1σ and the horizontal error bars correspond to the 95% interval of confidence on the
636 estimation of the relative abundances of *F. profunda*.

637

638 **Figure 3:** Nannoflora and geochemical proxies along core LC21. A) Blue line and associated
639 diamonds symbols represent the relative abundances of *F. profunda*. The dark blue shaded
640 area gives the 95% interval of confidence of the estimation of the relative abundances of *F.*
641 *profunda*. The absolute concentrations of coccoliths are depicted by the dotted green line and
642 associated diamonds symbols. The error bar, represent the 1σ standard error (calculated from
643 5 to 15 different counts for the same sample). The red arrow along the Y-axis depicts the
644 modern values around the LC21 site for the relative abundances of *F. profunda*. B) Relative
645 abundances of *H. carteri*, the dark blue shaded area gives the 95% interval of confidence of
646 the estimation of the relative abundances of *H. carteri*. C) $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ (black circles) and
647 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ loess smoothed (heavy black line). D) Organic carbon (C_{org}) content. E)
648 $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_{pachyderma-ruber}$ (black circles) and $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_{pachyderma-ruber}$ loess smoothed (heavy black line).
649 F) $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{pachyderma}$ (blue circles) and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{pachyderma}$ loess smoothed (heavy blue line). G)
650 $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{pachyderma}$ (green circles) and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{pachyderma}$ loess smoothed (heavy green line).

651

652 **Figure 4:** Comparison of the surface proxy derived from the relative abundances of *F.*
653 *profunda* with the planktonic foraminiferal geochemical proxies. Relative abundances of *F.*
654 *profunda*, here in logarithmic scale as depicted in equation 1, versus the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$. The
655 vertical error bars represent the external precision and the horizontal error bars the 1σ (related
656 to values calculated from equation 1). We prefer to discard the 8 first pre-S5 samples (open
657 green circles) as the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ values have the icevolume imprint of the Termination II.

658 **Auxiliary material**

659 **Table S1:** Surface sediment samples data set used in this study. The relative abundances of
660 *F. profunda* are from: ⁽¹⁾ this study, ⁽²⁾ [Knappertsbusch, 1993], ⁽³⁾ [Incarbona *et al.*, 2008]
661 and ⁽⁴⁾ [Malinverno, 2000]. The concentration of Chl-a were extracted from *Feldman and*
662 *McClain* [2011], except for the BANSIC / ANSIC cruises [Incarbona *et al.*, 2008]. The
663 samples that we used for our reconstruction in Figure 2C (red circles) are set in bold.

664

665 **Figure S1:** From top to bottom: relative abundances of *F. profunda* in core LC21, LC21
666 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ (black circles) and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$ loess smoothed (heavy black line), ODP 971A $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{ruber}$
667 (grey circles and line), LC21 $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{pachyderma}$ (black circles) and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{pachyderma}$ loess smoothed
668 (heavy black line), and ODP 971A $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{pachyderma}$ (grey circles and line). The vertical dashed
669 line depicts the termination of the dry interlude [Rohling *et al.*, 2002]. The LC21 record has
670 been transferred onto the 971A-equivalent scale following *Marino et al.* [2007].

